

Effect of Cowpea (*Vigna sinensis* L.) with Maize (*Zea mays* L.) Intercropping on Yield and Its Components

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Abstract—A field experiment was carried out at Arab El-Awammer Research Station, Agric. Res. Center, Assiut Governorate during summer seasons of 2013 and 2014. The present study assessed the effect of cowpea with maize intercropping on yield and its components. The experiment comprised of three treatments (sole cowpea, sole maize and cowpea-maize intercrop). The experimental design was a randomized complete block with four replications. Results indicated that intercropped maize plants with cowpea, exhibited greater potentiality and resulted in higher values of most of the studied criteria viz., plant height, number of ears/plant, number of rows/ear, number of grains/row, grains weight/ear, 100-grain weight and straw and grain yields. Fresh and dry forage yields of cowpea were lower in intercropping with maize than sole. Furthermore, the combined of the two seasons revealed that the total Land Equivalent Ratio (LER) between cowpea and maize was 1.65. The Aggressivity (A) maize was 0.45 and cowpea was -0.45. This showed that maize was the dominant crop, whereas cowpea was the dominated. The Competitive Ratio (CR) indicated that maize more competitive than cowpea, maize was 1.75 and cowpea was 0.57. The Actual Yield Loss (AYL) maize was 0.05 and cowpea was -0.40. The Monetary Advantage Index (MAI) was 2360.80.

Keywords—Intercropping, cowpea, maize, land equivalent ratio (LER).

I. INTRODUCTION

INTERCROPPING is a type of mixed cropping and defined as agricultural practice of cultivating two or more crops in the same space at the same time. The important reason to grow two or more crops together may be increase of productivity per unit of land. In intercropping system, all the environmental resources utilized to maximize crop production per unit area and per unit time. Thus, intercropping systems can provide many benefits through increased efficiency of land use, enhancing the capture and use of light, water and nutrients, controlling weeds, insects, diseases and increasing the length of production cycles. Other benefits of intercropping may be improve quality of the seed, and better control of water quality through minimizing the use of inorganic N fertilizers, replacing them by the use of legumes [1].

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There is a shortage of summer forage crops production in Egypt. Defoliation of maize is commonly used to feed animals. This resulted in decreasing maize yield. Hence, intercropping of forage crops with cereal crops, e.g. maize, sorghum and millet reduce the green fodder gap during summer season.

Maize is ranked third after wheat and rice among the most important cereal crops. In the USA maize is considered the king of cereal crops [2]. In Egypt, maize is essential for human and live-stocks consumption as a major source of carbohydrates, oil, as well as a minor source of protein. It is required for several industrial purposes such as starch and oil. At the same time, cowpea is an important legume crop. It is a primary source of plant protein for humans and animals. Cowpea can be used as a cover crop and to fix nitrogen in the soil [3].

Therefore, the main target of this research was to study the effect of cowpea with maize intercropping on yield and its components. Previous studies indicated that intercropping cowpea with maize significantly increased plant height in both crops and grain yield of maize in the first season and reduced it in the second season, but cowpea yield was reduced in the both seasons [4]. Grain yield of cowpea was reduced by 43% and 33% in intercropping and relay cropping, respectively [5]. Intercropping maize with runner bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) gave the highest-equivalent yield productive efficiency, land equivalent ratio, net returns and monetary advantage index [6]. Yield increased in a maize/soybean strip intercropping arrangement were primarily due to the upsurge in the boarder rows of maize together to soybeans [7]. Land equivalent ratio, Aggressivity, Competitive ratio and Actual yield loss were higher, in addition, there was a significant economic benefit expressed with higher Monetary advantage index values have been used to describe competition between component crops of intercropping systems [8]. Maize intercropped with cowpea produced the highest grain yield and the lowest values of associated weeds [9]. Grain yield of maize was observed the highest when maize intercropping with cowpea cultures. In monoculture the yield of cowpea was higher than yield of cowpea, while the lowest yield was obtained when cowpea sown with maize. The highest land equivalent ratio was obtained from corn with cowpea [10]. Maize, sorghum or millet grain yields were increased, or slightly affected by intercropping system compared with the sole crop, but that of legume crop yields (cowpea, bean) showed decrement of 50% [11]. The combined yield from the intercropping system was

higher than the total yielding of any the crops in pure stand. The reduction in intercropped maize yield ranged from 10 to 15% of the pure stand compared with a higher reduction ranging from 45 to 67 % in legume crops (cowpea and bean) pure stand yields [12]. Forage dry weights achieved by the intercrops were greater than those by either maize or cowpea sole crops [13]. Intercropping resulted in an increase in maize plant height especially when the intercropped crops were planted at the same of maize planting date [14]. Yield and of maize either intercropped with legume were the highest as sole crop, moreover, 100% maize + 100% cowpea planting ratio had the highest land equivalent ratio [15]. Intercropping can be used as a tool to improve the competitive ability of a canopy with good suppressive characteristics [16]. Intercropping was advantageous relative to sole cropping as land equivalent ratio values were more than unity [17]. Sorghum plants, when intercropped with cowpea, exhibited greater potentiality and recorded higher values of most of the studied criteria including plant height and grain yield/plant. However, Grain yield per hectare was lower in intercropping pattern than solid pattern [18]. Intercropping also had significantly increased on the maize and cowpea Stover, with intercropping resulting in higher Straw yield compared to the sole crops. The land equivalent ratio also showed that intercropping had a major advantage over sole cropping; particularly, when the maize and cowpea are planted within the same basin [19]. Cowpea intercropped with maize at 1:1 row arrangement recorded the highest grain yield per plant and per hectare, which were significantly different from sole crops [20]. Cowpea yield was lower due to competitive effect of maize in the intercropping system [21]. Maize straw, grain yields and soybean yield were significantly increased by the intercropping [22]. Intercropping cereal and grain legume crops helps maintain and improve soil fertility, because crops such as cowpea, mung bean and soybean accumulate from 80 to 350 kg N/ha. The main advantage of intercropping is the more efficient utilization of the available resources and the increased productivity compared with each sole crop of the mixture [23]. On the other hand, there was decreased yield of maize due to intercropping of legumes namely cowpea [24]. Intercropping may result in decreases in yield of one or both of the individual crops in a mixture. Nevertheless, the productivity of a unit land area is improved by intercropping rather than monocultures [25]. Intercropping maize with cowpea was seen to be significantly decreased the ear length, dry ear weight, dry grain yield and dry total plant biomass [26]. The planting pattern of the maize and legume did not increase the yield of maize [27].

The vegetative biomass legume crops the highest when intercropped with maize [28]. Mixtures of maize-legume showed advantages in land use efficiency expressed as LER [29]. The vegetative growth of component crop in a mixture is affected by intercropping [30]. The highest grain yield was obtained from sole cropping, while the lowest yield was obtained when intercropped maize-cowpea. The land equivalent ratios were higher than one in all intercropping [31]. Maize/bean intercrop system, the bean component did

not significantly affect maize grain yield and yield components [32].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The current study was conducted in research field, Arab El-Awammer Research Station, Agric. Res. Center. Assiut Governorate, Egypt during the summer seasons 2013 and 2014. The field site is located between latitude 27° 05' and longitude 31° 64'. The soil of such experiment was sandy calcareous as presented in Table I.

TABLE I
PHYSICAL -CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOIL

Chemical soil properties	Mechanical properties		
pH	8.37	Sand (%)	89.9
Ec dsm ⁻¹	0.33	Clay (%)	3.0
CaCO ₃ (%)	30.9	Silt (%)	7.1
O.M. (%)	0.19	Class	Sandy
Total N (%)	0.003		
Av. P (ppm)	8.31		
K+	0.75		

O.M: organic matter and Av. P: Available Phosphorus in ppm.

* Agricultural Research Center Soil, Water & Environment Res. Institute Unit of Analysis & Studies

The current study included three treatments namely sole cowpea, sole maize and the intercrop of cowpea with maize, in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

Fig. 1 Cropping systems; (A) Sole cowpea; (B) Sole maize; (C) Intercrop

All other normal cultural practices of growing crops at Assiut Governorate were applied and dates of these practices are present in Table II.

TABLE II
APPLICATION DATES OF SOME CULTURAL PRACTICES OF GROWING CROPS IN THE FIRST AND THE SECOND AT ASSIUT GOVERNORATE

Cultural practices	2013	2014
Sowing of maize and cowpea	12/5/2013	5/5/2014
First cut of cowpea	12/7/2013	5/7/2014
Second cut of cowpea	22/8/2013	15/8/2014
Harvest of maize	2/9/2013	25/8/2014

Each block with sole cowpea, sole maize and cowpea+ maize intercrop was 4.20 m x 5 m (21 m²). Cowpea seeds variety (cv. Cream) and maize seeds variety (cv. Single cross 130) was sown at 25 cm within a row and 70 cm between rows. Cowpea+maize intercrops planting both crops on same row (100% cowpea + 100% maize).

The plots were irrigated by sprinkler irrigation. Weeds control and other agricultural practices were performed as recommended.

The fertilization requirements were calculated based on area of feddan, this is 4200 m². The feddan fertilization requirements were 150 kg N fed⁻¹, P₂O₅ (200 kg fed⁻¹) and K₂O (50 kg fed⁻¹). Nitrogen of ammonium nitrate in five equal doses, after 15-25- 35- 45 and 55 days from sowing for maize. Cowpea was fertilized with 40 kg N fed., ammonium nitrate after thinning.

Studied Traits

A. For Maize

The plants of each plot were harvested at the end of the growing season (110 days from planting) and the ears were separated, air dried for 2 weeks, then total weight of ears/plot and ten plants were chosen at random from each plot at harvest to determine

- 1- Plant height (cm)
- 2- Number of ears/plant
- 3- Ear length (cm)
- 4- Ear diameter (cm)
- 5- Number of rows/ear
- 6- Number of grains/row
- 7- Grains weight/ear (g)
- 8- 100-grain weight (g)
- 9- Grain yield (kg/fed.)
- 10- Straw yield (kg/fed.)

B. For Cowpea

Two cuts of cowpea were harvested (either sole or intercropping). Traits studied over all cuts

- 1- Plant height (cm)
- 2- Number of branches /m²
- 3- Fresh forage yield (ton/fed.)
- 4- Dry forage yield (ton/fed.)

C. Competitive Relationships

1. *Land Equivalent Ratio (LER)* which verifies the effectiveness of intercropping for using the resources of the environment compared to sole cropping as indicated by [33].

The LER values were calculated as: $LER = (LERM + LERC)$, where $LERM = YIM/YM$ and $LERC = YIC/YC$, where YM and YC are the yields of maize and cowpea as sole while YIM and YIC are the yields of maize and cowpea as intercrops, respectively.

2. *Aggressivity (A)* was used to determine the competitive relationship between two crops in a mixture as indicated by [34]. The Aggressivity was calculated as: $AM = (YIM/YM \times ZIM) - (YIC/YC \times ZIC)$, and $AC = (YIC/YC \times ZIC) - (YIM/YM \times ZIM)$ where: ZIM = sown proportion of crop maize (in maize intercropping with cowpea); ZIC = sown proportion of crop cowpea (in cowpea intercropping with maize)

3. *Competitive Ratio (CR)* gives more desirable competitive ability for the crops. The CR represents simply the ratio of individual LERs of the two component crops and takes into account the proportion of the crops on which they are initially sown as indicated by [35] The CR index was calculated using the following formula: $CRM = (LERM / LERC) (ZIC / ZIM)$ while $CRC = (LERC / LERM) (ZIM / ZIC)$.

4. *Actual Yield Loss (AYL)*, which gave more accurate information about the competition than the other indices between components of intercropping system. The AYL is the proportionate yield loss or gain of intercrops compared to sole crop as indicated by [36]. The AYL was calculated as: $AYL = AYLM + AYLC$, where $AYLM = \{(YIM/XIM) / (YM / XM)\} - 1$ and $AYLC = \{(YIC/XIC) / (YC / XC)\} - 1$, where X is the sown proportion of intercrop maize and cowpea.

5. *Monetary Advantage Index (MAI)* Suggests that the economic assessment should be terms of the value of land saved; this could probably be most assessed on the basis of the rentable value of this land. The MAI was calculated according to the formula, as indicated by [37].

$$MAI = \frac{\text{Value of combined intercrops} \times LER - 1}{LER}$$

With Egyptian currency (LE), maize Price was 2 LE/kg for grain yield and cowpea was 120 LE/ton for fresh forage yield of the two seasons.

Statistical Analysis

The obtained data in each season were statistically analyzed of a randomized complete blocks design according to procedures outlined as indicated by [38].

III. RESULTS

A. Effect of Cowpea with Maize Intercropping on Maize Characters

Data in Table III revealed that the cowpea with maize intercropping had significantly effect on the plant height and number of ears/plant in both seasons, as well as number of rows/ear and 100-grain weight in the second season only. The other studied traits either in the 1st season or in the 2nd season did not differ significantly affected by the cowpea with maize intercropping. Moreover, the combined intercropping had a highly significantly or significantly effect on the most of the

above studied traits except ear length, number grains/row, grains weight/ear and grain yield/fed. Here, the results indicated that the intercropping significantly increased plant

height, number of ears/plant, number of rows/ear, 100-grain weight, ear diameter and straw yield/fed., in the either 1st season and 2nd season and its combined over sole.

TABLE III
EFFECT OF COWPEA WITH MAIZE INTERCROPPING ON THE PLANT HEIGHT, YIELD AND ITS COMPONENTS OF MAIZE IN 2013 AND 2014 SEASONS AND ITS COMBINED

Season 2013										
Characters	Plant height (cm)	No. of ears/plant	Ear length (cm)	Ear diameter (cm)	No. of rows/ear	No. of grains/row	Grains weight/ear (g)	100-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (kg/fed.)	Straw yield (kg/fed.)
Treatments										
Sole maize	232.64	1.03	19.04	3.92	14.40	39.15	122.20	31.05	2246	2636
Intercropping cowpea + maize	235.47	1.05	19.70	4.03	15.00	40.85	140.40	32.20	2340	2721
F-test	**	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Season 2014										
Characters	Plant height (cm)	No. of ears/plant	Ear length (cm)	Ear diameter (cm)	No. of rows/ear	No. of grains/row	Grains weight/ear (g)	100-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (kg/fed.)	Straw yield (kg/fed.)
Treatments										
Sole maize	229.63	1.09	19.91	4.23	15.00	41.22	138.12	33.43	2420	2926
Intercropping cowpea + maize	233.98	1.10	20.36	4.41	15.60	42.62	155.99	35.07	2550	3004
F-test	**	**	NS	NS	**	NS	NS	*	NS	NS
Combined of the two seasons										
Characters	Plant height (cm)	No. of ears/plant	Ear length (cm)	Ear diameter (cm)	No. of rows/ear	No. of grains/row	Grains weight/ear (g)	100-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (kg/fed.)	Straw yield (kg/fed.)
Treatments										
Sole maize	231.14	1.06	19.47	3.98	14.70	40.18	130.16	32.24	2333	3706
Intercropping cowpea + maize	234.73	1.08	20.03	4.21	15.30	41.73	148.19	33.64	2445	3834
F-test	**	**	NS	*	**	NS	NS	**	NS	*

*, **: indicated the significantly and highly significantly at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of probability, respectively
NS: non-significant difference

B. Effect of Cowpea with Maize Intercropping on Cowpea Characters

Data in Table IV showed that the plant height and number of branches/plant had a highly significantly affected by the intercropping either in the 1st cut or in the 2nd cut in both seasons. Moreover, the fresh forage yield and dry forage yield had significantly either in the 1st cut or in the 2nd cut in the both seasons. The results indicated that the cowpea plant height (cm) surpassed in the intercropping either in the 1st cut or in the 2nd cut over the sole cowpea in both seasons. However, the cowpeas number of branches/plant, fresh forage yield and dry forage yield (ton/ fed.) surpassed in either 1st cut or in the 2nd cut over the cowpea with maize intercropping in both seasons.

C. Effect of Cowpea with Maize Intercropping on Competitive Relationships and Yield Advantages in 2013 and 2014 Seasons and Its Combined

1. Land Equivalent Ratio (LER)

Results in Table V showed that LER values were greater (1.59, 1.70 and 1.65) than one in the both seasons and the combined analysis. The results, also showed that maize was superior in the intercrop system where the relative yield was increased (1.04, 1.05 and 1.05) of the sole in the both seasons and the combined analysis. Cowpea was inferior companion crop where the relative yield was decreased (0.55, 0.65 and 0.60) of the sole in the both seasons.

2. Aggressivity (A)

The data of Aggressivity revealed that values of (A) of maize was (0.49, 0.40 and 0.45) of the sole in both seasons and the combined analysis. Cowpea was (-0.49, -0.40 and -0.45) of the sole in the both seasons and the combined analysis.

3. Competitive Ratio (CR)

The CR of maize was greater (1.89, 1.61 and 1.75) while the CR of cowpea which was less than one (0.52, 0.62 and 0.57).

4. Actual Yield Loss (AYL)

The AYL values of maize were positive, (+0.04, +0.05 and +0.05) indicating that there was increase in yield (4.0, 5.0 and 5.0%) when intercropping with cowpea in both seasons and the combined seasons were analyzed. Actual Yield Loss values of cowpea were negative (-0.45, -0.35 and -0.40) indicating that there was a decrease in yield (45, 35 and 40% of sole).

5. Monetary Advantage Index (MAI)

The MAI is an indicator of the economic feasibility of intercropping systems. These values of MAI were 2097.28, 2607.95 and 2360.80 in both seasons and the combined analyses.

TABLE IV
EFFECT OF COWPEA WITH MAIZE INTERCROPPING ON PLANT HEIGHT, NUMBER OF BRANCHES/PLANT, FRESH FORAGE YIELD AND DRY FORAGE YIELD OF COWPEA 2013 AND 2014 SEASONS

Treatments	Season 2013						Season 2014					
	First cut		Second cut		Mean cuts		First cut		Second cut		Mean cuts	
	Plant height (cm)	No. of branches/plant										
Sole cowpea	83.75	5.42	76.33	3.31	80.04	4.37	78.52	5.45	71.48	3.66	75.00	4.56
Intercropping cowpea + maize	127.68	2.75	96.51	1.53	112.10	2.14	106.96	2.90	92.78	1.94	99.87	2.42
F-test	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

Treatments	Season 2013				Season 2014				Combined					
	First cut		Second cut		First cut		Second cut		First cut		Second cut		Total cut	
	Fresh forage yield (ton/fed.)	Dry forage yield (ton/fed.)	Fresh forage yield (ton/fed.)	Dry forage yield (ton/fed.)	Fresh forage yield (ton/fed.)	Dry forage yield (ton/fed.)	Fresh forage yield (ton/fed.)	Dry forage yield (ton/fed.)	Fresh forage yield (ton/fed.)	Dry forage yield (ton/fed.)	Fresh forage yield (ton/fed.)	Dry forage yield (ton/fed.)	Fresh forage yield (ton/fed.)	Dry forage yield (ton/fed.)
Sole cowpea	9.37	1.81	5.27	1.16	14.64	2.97	10.33	2.21	5.57	1.34	15.90	3.56		
Intercropping cowpea + maize	5.69	1.13	2.41	0.60	8.10	1.72	7.12	1.54	3.17	0.80	10.28	2.34		
F-test	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

*, **: indicated the significantly and highly significantly at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of probability, respectively
NS: non-significant difference

TABLE V
EFFECT OF COWPEA WITH MAIZE INTERCROPPING ON COMPETITIVE RELATIONSHIPS AND YIELD ADVANTAGES IN 2013 AND 2014 SEASONS AND ITS COMBINED

Characters	Season 2013												
	Yield/fed.		Land Equivalent Ratio (LER)			Aggressivity (A)		Competitive Ratio (CR)		Actual Yield Loss (AYL)			Monetary Advantage Index (MAI)
	maize kg/fed.	cowpea ton/fed.	LERM	LERC	total	AM	AC	CRM	CRC	AYLM	AYLC	total	
Sole	2246	14.64											
Intercropping cowpea + maize	2340	8.10	1.04	0.55	1.59	0.49	-0.49	1.89	0.52	0.04	-0.45	-0.41	2097.28

Season 2014													
Sole	2420	15.90											
Intercropping cowpea + maize	2550	10.28	1.05	0.65	1.70	0.40	-0.40	1.61	0.62	0.05	-0.35	-0.30	2607.95

Combined of the two seasons													
Sole	2333	15.27											
Intercropping cowpea + maize	2445	9.19	1.05	0.60	1.65	0.45	-0.45	1.75	0.57	0.05	-0.40	-0.35	2360.80

IV. DISCUSSION

The height of maize plant under intercropping system was more than that in the sole maize may be due to competition of associated crops for intercepted the light intensity, Therefore, its lead to the increase in maize plant. Moreover, the highest grain yield of intercropped maize may be due to the highest values for number of ears/plant, ear length, number of rows/ear, number of grains/row and 100-grain weight, since an important yield components caused in increasing the grain yield/fed at compared the sole maize. Moreover, cowpea plantation in such agro-ecosystem can be played as a reservoir for the naturally occurring biological control agents (As in Fig. 2). Intercropping is the best cropping system, because at this system light interception, soil moisture, soil temperature and yield were higher compared to sole crops. Microclimatic variation in intercropping system have caused favorable environmental conditions, ready for growth and high yield compared to sole crops [15]. Also, [18] mentioned that sorghum intercropped with cowpea exhibited greater potentiality and recorded higher values of plant height and

grain yield/plant. However, Grain yield per hectare was lower in intercropping pattern than solid pattern. Moreover, [23] found that intercropping cereal and grain legume crops helps maintain and improve soil fertility, because crops such as cowpea, mung bean and soybean accumulate from 80 to 350 kg N/ha. The main advantage of intercropping is the more efficient utilization of the available resources and the increased productivity compared with each sole crop of the mixture. These results are conformity to those reported by [4], [7], [9], [11], [14], [16], [19], [20]. They mentioned that cowpea intercropped with maize at 1:1 row arrangement recorded the highest grain yield per plant and per hectare, which were significantly different from sole crops. However, [27], [32] found that in a maize/bean intercrop system the bean component does not significantly affect maize grain yield and yield components. On the other hand, [24], [26] reported that intercropping maize with cowpea was seen to significantly decrease ear length, dry ear weight and dry grain yield at the same of maize planting date.

Fig. 2 Spotted ladybird on maize plants intercropped with cowpea

The cowpea plant height was higher in intercrop than that in sole cowpea. This finding is logic, since the light competition inter-and intra-plants of cowpea and the maize under intercropping. It is clear that the competition between the two-associated crops amplified by maize elongation and consequently its large shading on cowpea. In addition, the reduction in green forage yield was higher in the second cut than in the first cut compared with solid plant in both seasons. The large reduction in the second cut due to the highest competition of maize with shading effect of the taller component maize, which obstructed solar radiation from penetrating into the lower cowpea canopy, the lowest shading of young maize plants on cowpea accompanies with the lowest competitions and in consequence lowest forage yield reduction. The maximum growth and yield of cowpea was observed in single cropping. They added that the stem dry weight reduced by 52% in intercropping as compared to single cropping [5]. These results are consistent with those obtained by [11], [12], [21]. On the other hand, [13] mentioned that forage dry weights achieved by the intercrops were greater than those by either maize or cowpea sole crops. Also, [22] reported that the highest straw yield was obtained under the sole crop at compared by the intercropping crops. Similar results were also reported by [19], [28], [30].

Data in Table V indicated that LER, A, CR, AYL and MAI varied considerably due to the effect of intercropping cowpea on maize. The LER it could be concluded that actual productivity was higher the expected productivity. Aggressivity revealed that values of maize were positive, whereas it was negative for cowpea. It showed that maize was the dominant crop and cowpea was the dominated crop in the both seasons and the combined analyses. The CR indicated that the maize was dominant crop and more competitive than cowpea. Similar trend to that of LER, A and CR was also observed for AYL in Table V. In particular, AYL for maize was positive value in both seasons and the combined analysis.

When intercropping with cowpea, which indicates a yield advantage for maize probably because of the positive effect of cowpea on maize when grown in association. While AYL values of cowpea was negative when intercropping on maize, which indicated a yield advantage. These values of MAI were positive due to LER and CR was greater than one. Similar results were observed by [6], [8], [10], [14], [15], [17], [19], [29], [31].

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the productivity of a unit land area is improved by intercropping rather than monocultures. Intercropping can be used as a tool to improve competitive ability of a canopy with good suppressive characteristics. Results indicated that cowpea with maize intercrop produced greater grain yield than maize sole crop. The LER also showed that intercropping had a major advantage over sole cropping particularly when the maize and cowpea were planted within the same basin. We recommend that planting of cowpea with maize mixture should be 100% cowpea: 100% maize (cowpea intercrop on the other side of maize rows).

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REFERENCES

- [1] KU. Dhima, AA. Lithourgidis, IB. Vasilakoqlou, and CA. Dordas. Competition indices of common vetch and cereals intercropping in two seeding ratio. *Field Crops Res.* vol., 100. pp. 249-258. 2007.
- [2] M. Dahmardeh, A. Ghanbari, B. Syasar and M. Ramroudi. Effect of intercropping maize with cowpea on green forage yields and quality evaluation. *Asian J. Plant Sci.* vol., 8. pp. 235-239. 2009.
- [3] J. A. N. Asiwe, D. Belane, and F. D. Dakora. Evaluation of cowpea breeding lines for nitrogen fixation at ARC Grain crops institute, Potchefstroom, South Africa. Abstract of the 16th International Congress on Biological Nitrogen Fixation, Montana, USA pp. 14-19. 2009.
- [4] D. A. Okpara. Growth and yield of maize and vegetable cowpea as influenced by intercropping and nitrogen fertilizer in the low land humid tropics. *J. Sustainable Agric. and the Environ.* Vol., 2. pp.188-194. 2000.
- [5] Polthanee Anan and Surachet Butchareon. Comparison of single cropping, intercropping and relay cropping of corn with cowpea under rainfed conditions in an upland area of northeastern Thailand. *J. ISSAAS* vol., 6. pp.1-12. 2000.
- [6] A. K. Padhi. Effect of vegetable intercropping on productivity, economics and energetics of maize (*zea mays*). *Indian J. Agron.* Vol., 46. pp. 204-210. 2001.
- [7] L. Li, J. Sun, F. Zhang, X. Li, S. Yang and Z. Rengel. Wheat/maize or wheat/soybean strip intercropping I yield advantage and interspecific interaction on nutrients. *Field Crop Res.*, vol., 71. pp. 123-137. 2001.
- [8] P. K. Ghosh. Growth, yield competition and economics of groundnut/cereal fodder intercropping systems in the semi-arid tropics of India. *Field Crops Res.* vol., 88. pp.227-237. 2004.
- [9] A. A. Zohry. Effect of preceding winter crops and Intercropping on yield, yield components and associated Weeds in maize. *Annals of Agric. Sc., Moshtohor*, vol., 43. pp. 139-148. 2005.
- [10] S. M. Shata, Safaa, A. Mahmoud and Hanan, S. Siam. Improving calcareous soil productivity by integrated effect of intercropping and

- fertilizer dorycnium rectum. Res. J. of Agri. and Biolo. Sciences, vol., 3. pp.733-739. 2007.
- [11] F. Yilmaz, M. Atak and M. Erayman. Identification of advantages of maize- legume intercropping over stoccy cropping through competition indices in the East Mediterranean Region. Turk. J. Agric. Vol., 32. pp.111-119. 2007.
- [12] M. A. Abou-Keriasha, M.A. Abd El-Hady and F.R. Nawar. Response of some cowpea varieties to intercropping with maize under upper Egypt condition. Egypt. J. App. Sci. vol., 24. pp. 495-514. 2009.
- [13] Hamdollah Eskandari and Ahmad Ghanbari. Intercropping of Maize (*Zea mays*) and Cowpea (*Vigna sinensis*) as Whole-Crop Forage: Effect of Different Planting Pattern on Total Dry Matter Production and Maize Forage Quality. Not. Bot. Hort. Agrobot. Cluj. Vol., 37. pp.152-155. 2009.
- [14] M. A. Abou-Keriasha, A. Sahar Sherif and KH. Wafaa Mohamed. Maize grain yield response to intercropping with three legume fodder crops. Egypt. J. Agric. Res. vol., 88. pp.1259-1276. 2010.
- [15] Ahmed Ghanbari, Mehdi Dahmardeh, Barat Ali Siahsar and Mahmoud Ramroudi. Effect of maize (*Zea mays* L.) - cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L.) intercropping on light distribution, soil temperature and soil moisture in arid environment. Journal of Food, Agriculture & Environment. Vol., 8. pp. 102-108. 2010.
- [16] M. Rezvani, F. Zaeafarian, M. Aghaalkhani, H. Rahimian Mashhadi and E. Zand. Investigation Corn and Soybean intercropping advantages in competition with redroot pigweed and jimsonweed. World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology, vol., 5. pp.327-329. 2011.
- [17] J. Sarkodie-Addo and Abdul-Rahaman. Spatial arrangements and time of introducing an intercrop on the productivity of component crops in maize (*Zea mays* L.) – soybean (*Glycine max* L. Merrill) intercropping systems. Inter. J. of Sci. and Adva. Tech. vol., 2. pp.103-107. 2012.
- [18] Y. A. Refay, A. A. Alderfasi, M. M. Selim and k. Awad. Evaluation of variety, cropping pattern and plant density on growth and yield production of grain sorghum-cowpea under limited water supply condition growth, yield and yield component characters of sorghum. J. of Agric. and Veterinary Science, vol., 2. pp.24-29. 2013.
- [19] E. D. N. Dube, T. Madanzi, A. Kapenzi and E. Masvaya. Root length density in maize/cowpea intercropping under a basin tillage system in a semi-arid area of zimbabwe. American Journal of Plant Sciences. vol., 5. pp. 1499-1507. 2014.
- [20] Iderawumi abdulraheem mukhtar. Effect of cowpea on growth and yield parameter in a maize-cowpea intercrop. Journal of Management and Science. Vol., 4. pp. 37-42. 2014.
- [21] ET. Sebetha, AT. Modi and LG. Owoeye. Maize-cowpea rotation and intercropping effects on cowpea yield. Ph. D. Thesis, University of KwaZulu- Natal. 2014.
- [22] J. M. M. Matusso, J. N. Mugwe and M. Mucheru-Muna. Effects of different maize (*Zea mays* L.)–Soybean (*Glycine max* L. Merrill) intercropping patterns on yields and its economics. Academia Journal of Agricultural Research. Vol., 2. pp.159-166. 2014.
- [23] Hamid Reza Mobasser, Mohammad Reza Vazirimehr and Khashayar Rigi. Effect of intercropping on resources use, weed management and forage quality. Inter. J. of Plant, Animal and Environmental Sciences, vol., 4. pp.707-713. 2014.
- [24] K. S. Gangwar, and S. K. Sharma. Fodder legume intercropping in maize (*Zea mays*) and its effect on succeeding wheat (*Triticum aestivum*). Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences, vol., 64. pp.38-40. 1994.
- [25] Y. A. Abayomi. Influence of height of maize variety on the productivity of intercropped maize (*Zea mays* L.) and cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp). Ghana Jnl arie. Vol., 33. pp. 199-206. 2000.
- [26] O. M. Egbe, S. E. Alibo, and I. Nwueze. Evaluation of some extra-early- and early- maturing cowpea varieties for intercropping with maize in southern guinea savannah of Nigeria. Agriculture and Biology Journal of North America. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5251/abjna.2010.1.5.845.858>. 2010.
- [27] Thayamini H. S. and I. Brintha. Review on maize based intercropping. J. of Agro. Vol., 9. pp.135-145. 2010.
- [28] R. N. Amos, B. A. Jens and M. Symon. On farm evaluation of yield and economic benefits of short term maize legume intercropping systems under conservation Agriculture in Malawi. Field crop research, vol., 132. pp.149-157. 2012.
- [29] Hamdollah Eskandari. Intercropping of maize (*zea mays*) with cowpea (*vigna sinensis*) and mungbean (*vigna radiata*): effect of complementarity of intercrop components on resource consumption, dry matter production and legumes forage quality. J. Basic. Appl. Sci. Res., vol., 2. pp. 355-360. 2012.
- [30] K. Mangasini, L. M. Mwanahawa, G. M. Arbogast and P. K. Neema. Agronomic factors limiting groundnut production: A case of smallholder farming in Taboraregion. 17th Annual Research Workshop Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, pp. 28-29. 2012.
- [31] F. O. Takim. Advantages of maize-cowpea intercropping over sole cropping through competition indices. Journal of Agriculture and Biodiversity Research, vol., 1. pp. 53-59. 2012.
- [32] O. M. Kitonyo, G.N. Chemining'wa and J.W. Muthomi. Productivity of farmer-preferred maize varieties intercropped with beans in semi-arid Kenya. International Journal of Agronomy and Agricultural Research. Vol., 3. pp.6-16. 2013.
- [33] R. W. Willey and S.O. Osiru. Studies on mixture of maize and beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) with particular reference to plant populations. J. Agric. Sci. Camb. Vol., 79. pp. 519-529. 1972.
- [34] C. A. Mc-Gilchrist. Analysis and competition experiments. Biometrics, Vol., 21. pp. 975- 985. 1960.
- [35] R. W. Willey and M. R. Rao. Competitive ratio for quantifying competition between intercrops. Exp. Agric. f6. pp.117-125. 1980.
- [36] P. Banik. Evaluation of wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) and legume intercropping under 1:1 and 2:1 row replacement series system. J. Agron. & Crop Sci. vol., 176. pp. 289-294. 1996.
- [37] R.W. Willey. Intercropping its importance and research needs. Part I: Competition and yield advantages. Field Crop Abst. Vol., 32. pp.1-10. 1979.
- [38] K. A. Gomez and A. A. Gomez. Statistical procedures for agriculture research 2nd ed. John Wiley and Sons. New York, pp. 317-333. 1984.